

FORMATION AND LEGAL GENESIS OF THE INSTITUTE OF APPEALS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the formation and legal genesis of the institution of appeal, including the constitutional norms of the right to appeal in Uzbekistan and regulatory legal documents in this area.*

Key words : *appeals, appeals of individuals , appeals of legal entities, Institute of appeals of individuals and legal entities.*

If we look at the history of world statehood, the institution of appeals is the implementation of the rights of individuals in any country and the restoration of their violated rights, administration of power, ensuring the rule of law, increasing the responsibility of officials, fighting corruption, and bringing closer the relationship between the population and the state. and they served as an important tool in solving problems such as being aware of their situation.

The formation of this institution goes back to the distant past, that is, to the primitive community system from which humanity arose. Because at that time, people unconditionally followed the rules of behavior and behavior that were followed in the society. Also, a certain solution was reached when they complained to the clan elder or tribal chief because of the realization of their rights, discrimination or humiliation.

Similarly, clan elders or tribal chiefs effectively used the suggestions of experienced, elderly people or kaiwanis in carrying out the administration. However, before the emergence of statehood or writing, complaints and proposals were verbally expressed in content.

The written form of this institution dates back to the time when writing was discovered (the state of Sumer in the middle of the 4th millennium BC). [1;20] appeared, and during the gradual process of states or empires, its geography expanded further, progress shifts have been achieved. The electronic form began to be put into practice in the 21st century, that is, along with the development of information and communication technologies.

If we look at the history of statehood, we can find a number of sources about the effective use of the institution of appeals by the rulers in the process of power management in the past.

For example, the famous philosopher Marcus Tullius Cicero encouraged citizens to be active in the management of state and community affairs throughout his life. He gained the trust

of the people by speaking openly to authorized persons about the illegal activities and abuses committed by the representatives of the authorities in his practical activities [2;408-409] .

In the work "Politics" of Nizamulmulk, who worked in the position of Prime Minister, who made a great contribution to the establishment of a centralized and powerful state of the Seljuk kings, it is possible to accept appeals, solve them fairly, send replies in time , and receive those who come with appeals as much as possible. theoretical and practical ways of increasing, organizing their reception at a high level, strengthening the country, building a disciplined and stable state, bringing closer the relationship between the population and the state, fighting against abuses, and forming a fair government published by [3;20,122,129,230] .

The development and directions of development of this institution were manifested in the history of Uzbekistan in unique ways. For example, according to the sources, "During the reign of the Khorezmshahs, the position of " **Qissadar** " was introduced in the sultanate. He collected the applications and complaints received by the sultan during the week and submitted them to the ruler on Friday night. About the result of consideration of the appeal, each applicant or complainant was given an appropriate answer" [4;145] .

State officials regularly went to the places and organized dialogues with the population, this method was used to inform about the situation of the citizens. In particular, it is written in the sources that Temur Malik, the governor of Khojand region under the rule of the Khorezmshahs, communicated with the residents of Kurkat village in this region and got acquainted with the people's condition, living conditions and lifestyle [5;90-91] .

In the reign of Amir Temur, who established a powerful centralized state, a somewhat improved mechanism of the institution of appeals was formed. In particular, the legal norms related to working with appeals are reflected in the "Temur Laws", which is considered the main law of the country, which "specifies a special procedure for receiving petitioners, formalizing and reviewing appeals . A special structure dealing with petitions, namely the position of " **arzbegi** ", was established, and it was to inform the ruler about the condition of the soldiers, raiyats and those who came to petition, the prosperity of the country, which of the important works had been completed or not. was considered the person responsible for informing" [6;24] .

During the rule of Amir Temur, special reception rooms of the ruler were established in each city and each castle to receive those who came with appeals, and these were called "borgoh" [7;507] or "Court of Complaints and Complaints" [8;48] .

The law of this state provides for the inevitability of punishment against officials who make mistakes in matters related to the appeal. In particular, in order to inform the ruler about

the real situation in the localities, including the attitudes and actions of local authorities and civil servants towards the people, separate "informer" positions were introduced in each region, and these are the only a special decree was issued that "fingers of those who typed should be cut off" in case of sending false news [9;53] .

dodkhoh " , who deals directly with appeals, has been introduced. He is responsible for bringing the appeals of the applicants to the emir and receiving the answer. [4;294] . In addition, Udaichilar (informers to the emir) and Mirza-munshi (head of the emir's private reception) are responsible for working with appeals . such individual officials worked [10;7] .

In "Essays of the Khanate of Bukhara" written by the Russian historian NAMAev, important information is given about the procedure for receiving applicants by the emir of Bukhara. In particular, he said that "... once a week, the khan personally holds a reception for those who come with an application, the public is informed about this one to two hours before the reception, the applicants are invited to the khan's palace and are invited to the reception. will be admitted to a special room, the Amir will hear and respond to the requests or complaints of the applicants. Although there is no timetable for the reception day, the reception ceremony usually lasted 15-30 minutes" [11;9] , he says.

So, these countries use this institution, *firstly*, to give citizens the opportunity to apply directly to the higher authorities in order to protect their rights and freedoms, and *secondly* , to allow the population to participate in the state administration to a certain extent. used to create conditions, *thirdly* , the social situation in places, that is, the way of living of citizens, to determine the relationship of responsible persons to the ordinary population, and to determine the practical implementation of the laws in force in the country. It establishes that a complaint against the conduct of an official or civil servant by the rulers of the state in a civil society is acted upon without any threat.

However, if we look at the history of legislation, the idea of human rights first appeared in England. For example, the Magna Carta, adopted in 1215, is the earliest Constitution signed to guarantee a special right to social status by lords, that is, aristocrats, over the king. "Petition of Rights" adopted in 1628, "Bill of Rights" in 1689 [12;99] , "Freedom of Information" Act adopted in Finland in 1766 [13; Norms such as 28] are historically very important.

Nevertheless, the concept of "fundamental rights and freedoms of man and citizen" was strengthened by law only in the 18th century. It sounded for the first time in the 1789 French Declaration of Human and Citizen Rights [14;201] . It is also reflected in the French Constitution [1;283] (1791) and other documents. This served as the basis for the formation of the right to

appeal.

The right to petition was established as a constitutional provision for the first time in 1789 in the First Amendment to the US Constitution, which stated that "...no law shall be made abridging the right of the people to petition the government for redress of their grievances," and thereby The noble idea that "the constitution should serve the people, not the people the constitution" [15; 183] was reinforced.

It is worth noting that the institution of appeals developed and improved in its own way in the countries that operated at different stages of human society, but until the second half of the 20th century, the superiority of the rules of social relations in this area was generally recognized by all countries. not received.

The results of the Second World War marked a turning point in the international protection of human rights and freedoms, including the right to appeal. In particular, Article 8 of the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" adopted on December 10, 1948 states, "Every person has the right to the effective restoration of these rights by competent national courts in cases of violations of the fundamental rights granted to him by the constitution or by law" [16; 243], the rule was established.

This, in turn, became the basis for imposing important obligations on the protection of human rights on the countries of the world that recognized the supremacy of the generally recognized rules of this international law.

On the basis of this declaration, the "International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights", "International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights", which was adopted on December 19, 1966 and entered into force in 1976, and the Optional Protocol to this Covenant [17; 8] requirements laid the foundation for the emergence of a separate institution of non-judicial or public authority legal protection of the right to appeal, which is a component of human rights and freedoms.

In particular, in Article 2, Clause 3 of Part II of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, it is the responsibility of the states participating in this Covenant: a) if the rights and freedoms of a person, whose rights and freedoms are recognized in this Covenant, are violated , to provide him with effective means of legal protection, even if these violations are committed by people acting in an official capacity; b) to ensure that the right to such protection is determined by a competent court, administrative authority or other legislative authority or by any other authoritative body provided for in the legal system of the state for any person seeking legal protection, and to ensure the possibility of legal protection increase; s) in the cases where

the legal protection means are given, the authoritative administration is obliged to ensure their implementation [17; 34-35] .

Therefore, in the 1978 Constitution of the Uzbek SSR, adopted on the basis of the requirements of these international documents, the right to submit an application, proposal and complaint has a constitutional character. Because the constitutional norms of the right to appeal were strengthened in Articles 35, 47 and 56 of this Basic Law [18; 12-16] . However, in these legal norms, the right to appeal to state bodies and judicial bodies is defined in a general manner.

No special laws have been adopted regarding the implementation of these legal norms specified in the Constitution. However, social relations regarding the right to appeal to state bodies are regulated by the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR of March 4, 1980 "On the procedure for consideration of proposals, applications and complaints of citizens" [19; 173-178] and guarantee of legal protection of rights and freedoms of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the USSR dated April 18, 1986 "On the liability of officials for violation of the procedure for consideration of proposals, applications and complaints of citizens and prosecution for criticism, it is correct to apply the law by the courts on" is regulated by Resolution No. 9 [20; 114-118] .

It is worth noting that in the constitution of the authoritarian regime, "the essence of the limitation of human rights is in the political sphere: in the political-legal relations between the state and the individual, state law is the highest, and human rights are second. This means that political rights are limited. The state has decided the important issues in the life of the society by itself. Although attention is paid to the participation of a person in the affairs of state administration, to express his opinion, the main decisive verdict is issued by the state. As a result, the place and role of the people was degraded. The constitution was subordinated to the political programs and ideology of the single ruling party [21; 30-31] .

During the past period of Uzbekistan's independence, the constitutional foundations for the protection of human rights and freedoms were created. In particular, the right to appeal as a component of the constitutional right has been brought into a comprehensive system, and in Article 40 of Chapter VIII of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Section II entitled " Political Rights " , it is stated that " everyone directly and together with others to state bodies and organizations, Citizens have the right to apply to self-governing bodies, officials or people's representatives with applications, proposals and complaints. Applications, suggestions and complaints must be considered in accordance with the procedure and within the time limits specified by the law .

This constitutional norm was put into practice with the new version of the Law O'RQ-445 of September 11, 2017 "On Appeals of Natural and Legal Entities " Resolution No. 7 of January 5, 2018 "On Approval of the Model Regulation on the Procedure for Working with Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities in Self-Governing Bodies of Citizens" and Resolution No. 7 of May 7, 2018 "In State Bodies, State Institutions and State-Participated It is defined in the Decision No. 341 "On approval of the model regulation on the procedure for working with appeals of individuals and legal entities in organizations" .

Also, as a reliable guarantee of the right to appeal, in Article 55 of the Constitution, " Everyone has the right to protect his rights and freedoms by all methods not prohibited by law."

Everyone is guaranteed the right to protect their rights and freedoms through the court, to appeal to the court against illegal decisions, actions and inaction of state bodies and other organizations and their officials.

Everyone is guaranteed the right to have his/her case reviewed by a competent, independent and impartial court within the time limits established by law in order to restore his/her violated rights and freedoms.

In accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and international treaties, everyone has the right to apply to international bodies protecting human rights and freedoms, if all internal means of legal protection of the state have been used.

Everyone has the right to be compensated by the state for damages caused by illegal decisions, actions or inaction of state bodies or their officials . is being put into practice through the Code on

However, in recent years, the process of comprehensive reforms implemented in Uzbekistan has fundamentally reformed the legislation that regulates social relations in the field of appeals of individuals and legal entities and determines the procedure for working with appeals among all sectors. required to do.

Based on this, on September 25, 2016, an electronic reception [22;114] was established on the Prime Minister's Internet network and the Republic of Uzbekistan Requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Appeals of Natural and Legal Entities" of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 27, 2016 "Heads of Ministries and Agencies, Economic Associations, Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Governors of Regions, Cities and Districts" It is no exaggeration to say that Decision No. 366 "On the responsibility for unconditional performance" was literally the prelude to the further development of the appeals institution.

No. 4904 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 28, 2016 "On measures to radically improve the system of working with appeals of natural and legal entities" and "Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated February 7, 2017 Decree No. 4947 on the strategy of Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Appeals of Natural and Legal Entities" dated September 11, 2017, Law "On Administrative Procedures" dated January 8, 2018, Administrative Law dated January 25, 2018 the code of conduct of court proceedings , the Regulation of the Councils of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2019 on the procedure for submitting electronic collective appeals and their consideration through the web portal "My Opinion" The adoption of the Joint Resolution No. 2310-III/QQ-503-III and several other legislative documents related to the field serve to expand the scope of the institute of appeals.

a social and objective necessity to develop a perfect mechanism of the institutional system that ensures the guarantee of the right to appeal .

In this regard, the establishment of institutions such as People's receptions, Virtual reception of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Business ombudsman, Children's rights representative (ombudsman), Anti-corruption agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan further improved the mechanisms of implementation of the right to appeal.

Today, protecting the rights and freedoms of people and ensuring their legal interests against the background of comprehensive development of the appeals institute has become a priority task of the state of Uzbekistan.

This situation is also reflected in the documents defining the country's long-term perspective. In particular, the main idea of "Establishing a fair and modern state in the service of the people" was put forward in the Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 "On the strategy of "Uzbekistan-2030" No. PF-158". The 82nd goal of Chapter IV entitled "Ensuring the supremacy of law, organization of state administration in the service of the people" clearly defines the tasks to be implemented in the future in terms of further expanding the scope of the appeals institution.

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